

Foamy Oil Behavior of an Iranian Heavy Oil Reservoir

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Abstract

Foamy oil expression has puzzled many reservoir engineers in characterizing some heavy oil reservoirs. The strange fluid behavior of such reservoirs is considered as the reason of abnormally high flow rates and (the higher than expected) recovery factors. The authors aimed to briefly elaborate the foamy oil concept, review methodologies and laboratory experiments for identifying foamy oil behavior, and present a modified methodology for laboratory investigation of foamy behavior. The concern here is an Iranian heavy oil reservoir whose foamy nature is under debate (according to some production reports). Experimental results indicate that the studied crude oil acquires foamy characteristics, which makes it the first heavy oil reservoir with foamy behavior in the Middle East region.

Keywords: heavy oil, foamy crude, supersaturation, critical supersaturation, pseudo bubble point pressure.